

Stress Analysis of a Hybrid Flywheel Rotor Using a Modified Generalized Strain Assumption

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SUMMARY: A numerical method for calculating the stress and strength ratio distribution of the hybrid rim-type composite flywheel rotor is presented with a consideration of the thermally induced residual stresses. The axisymmetric rotor is divided into several rings and the stiffness matrix for each ring is derived by solving the radial equilibrium equation and the stress-strain-temperature relations. The ring stiffness matrices are assembled into a symmetric global matrix satisfying the continuity equations at each interface with the assumptions of a modified generalized plane strain. In the MGPS, the z-directional axial strains are assumed to linearly vary along the radial direction; $\mathbf{e}_z = \mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{e}_1 r$. The conditions that the z-directional force and the circumferential moment resultants vanish are thus used to solve the z-directional axial strains as well as the radial and circumferential strains. After solving the strain distributions, the on-axis stresses and the strength ratios are calculated at each ring. Three-dimensional finite element method (FEM) is then used to verify the accuracy of the present method. The results are also compared with those based on the assumption of a plane stress (PSS). In this case, the analysis of MGPS better matches with FEM results than PSS.

An optimum design is then performed maximizing total stored energy (TSE) with the thickness of each composite rim as design variables. The optimal design obtained in this study which consider material sequence provides a more effective way of maximizing TSE.

It is found out that the consideration of the residual stress in the design of the hybrid flywheel rotor is crucial. The result of the optimal designs show that TSE with consideration of DT reduces by about 30%.

KEYWORDS: Modified Generalized Plane Strain, Residual Stress, Hybrid Composite Flywheel Rotor, Optimization

INTRODUCTION

An advanced composite flywheel has recently attracted the considerable attention of many investigators for many energy storage applications including the electric utility, hybrid or electric vehicle and spacecraft [1-3]. The composite flywheel rotor has characteristics of distinctively high energy density, long life and light weight. The essential components of a

flywheel energy storage system are a composite flywheel rotor, motor/generator, power transforming electronics, magnetic bearing, and housing [4-6] as shown in Fig. 1. Recent efforts in development of the flywheel have been devoted to the experimental and theoretical research on increasing the performance and insuring the safety of the flywheel. Especially, along with technical innovations in high strength composite materials, many investigations have been devoted to increasing the total stored energy (TSE) using the composite materials in the flywheel [7-9].

Fig. 1 Flywheel energy storage system with a multi ringed composite rotor.

The various approaches for calculating the stress distribution of a composite rotor subjected to centrifugal forces have been cited in literature [7-9]. In manufacturing composite flywheel rotor, the curing residual stresses are caused by the curing process [10], and they have to be considered in the calculation of the stresses. However, methods for evaluating the effects of material properties and curing residual stress on the energy storage capability have not been pertinently addressed. Moreover, no investigation thus far has addressed how to optimally design the thickness of each composite rim considering both the material sequence and curing residual stresses.

In this study, an analysis using MGPS has been thus developed for the calculation of the stresses of the rotating composite flywheel rotor of varying material properties and curing residual stresses. An optimal design is also created maximizing the total stored energy together with considering the effects of the material sequence and thermally induced stresses due to curing. The thickness of each composite rim is considered as design variables. A structural analysis based on the 3-D finite element method is performed considering the rim-by-rim variation of material properties, the axial variation of stresses and displacements for verification of the results.

OPTIMIZATION

A proper combination of composite materials for the rotor could reduce the stress distribution in the rotor and eventually increase TSE. The objective of this study is to maximize TSE of a hybrid flywheel rotor without any material failure. Strength ratio R is used for failure analysis, where a value of R greater than 1 indicates material failure [11]. To ensure the rotor from any material failure, in this approach, strength ratio R calculated at any points of the rotor must have values less than 1. The inner radius r_1 of the rotor is given and the thickness t_m of each rim ($m=1,2,3,\dots,M$) is used as the design variables. M denotes the total number of composite rims. The design variables for the case of $M=3$, for example, are shown in Fig. 2.

The optimization is thus formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Find} & \quad t_m \quad (m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M) \\
\text{Maximize} & \quad E = \frac{1}{2} I \omega^2 \\
\text{Subject to} & \quad \text{Max } R < 1
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Fig. 2 Cross sectional view of the hybrid composite flywheel rotor; t_m are design variables in the optimization.

In Equation (1), I is a mass moment of inertia of the hybrid rotor. The total stored energy (TSE) E can be thus written in terms of the inner radius r_m and outer radius r_{m+1} of each rim:

$$E = \frac{\rho}{4} h \omega^2 \sum_{m=1}^M (r_{m+1}^4 - r_m^4) r_m \tag{2}$$

In Equation (2), the subscript m indicates each rim and the other variables include the length of the rotor h , the density of the m -th rim ρ_m , and the rotating speed ω .

Stress analysis should be performed in each rim to calculate the maximum strength ratio. For that purpose, in this study, each rim of thickness t_m is equally divided into N element rings, and stress analysis is performed on each element ring. The strength ratio are then calculated on the inner and outer surfaces of each element ring, i.e., $R_i^{(j)}$ and $R_o^{(j)}$ in the j -th ring.

In order to solve the nonlinear optimization problem formulated in Equation (1), the modified method of feasible directions for constrained minimization is used [12].

STRESS AND STRENGTH ANALYSIS

For a numerical calculation, the composite flywheel rotor of varying material properties is divided into many rings and each ring is assumed to have a constant material property of an angle-ply laminate. Based on the assumption of a modified generalized plane strain state, all the rings are free to expand or contract in the axial direction linearly. The flywheel rotor is also assumed cylindrically orthotropic, subject to axisymmetric centrifugal forces due to rotation and cool down from the cure temperature to room temperature. With the axisymmetric conditions, all the displacements and stresses are thus independent of the axial and circumferential directions. The radial equilibrium equation for each ring and the axial force equilibrium equation for the rotor are concurrently used and expressed in a stiffness matrix.

The stress distribution in each ring is governed by the radial equilibrium equation, which is written in cylindrical coordinates as [13]

$$\frac{d\mathbf{s}_r}{dr} + \frac{\mathbf{s}_r - \mathbf{s}_q}{r} + \mathbf{r}r\mathbf{w}^2 = 0 \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{s}_r and \mathbf{s}_q are the radial and circumferential stresses, respectively, \mathbf{r} denotes a density, and \mathbf{w} the rotational angular velocity. The stress-strain relation in the cylindrical coordinate system is written as

$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{a}DT) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{e} are the stress and strain vectors, respectively, \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{a} denotes a stiffness matrix and thermal expansion coefficient vector and DT the temperature change. Eq. (4) can be rewritten in the cylindrical coordinate system as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{s}_q \\ \mathbf{s}_z \\ \mathbf{s}_r \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & Q_{13} \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & Q_{23} \\ Q_{31} & Q_{32} & Q_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{e}_q \\ \mathbf{e}_z \\ \mathbf{e}_r \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{b}_q \\ \mathbf{b}_z \\ \mathbf{b}_r \end{pmatrix} \Delta T \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (5), the circumferential and radial strains are expressed by the r-direction displacement u_r , the z-directional axial strains are assumed to linearly vary along the radial direction in MGPS (Modified Generalized Plane Strain).

$$\mathbf{e}_q = \frac{u_r}{r}, \quad \mathbf{e}_r = \frac{\int u_r}{\int r} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{e}_z = \mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{e}_1 r \quad (6)$$

After substituting Eqs. (5) and (6) into Eq. (3), the radial displacement u_r can be solved, i.e.:

$$u_r = -\mathbf{r}\mathbf{w}^2 \mathbf{j}_0 r^3 + C_1 \mathbf{j}_1 r^k + C_2 \mathbf{j}_2 r^{-k} + \mathbf{j}_3 \mathbf{e}_1 r^2 + \mathbf{j}_4 \mathbf{e}_0 r + \mathbf{j}_{b_1} DT r \quad (7)$$

C_1 and C_2 in Eq. (7) are unknown constants to be determined from the boundary conditions, and \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{j}_i are defined in terms of the material properties:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{k} &= \sqrt{\frac{Q_{11}}{Q_{33}}}, \quad \mathbf{j}_0 = \frac{1}{(9 - \mathbf{k}^2)Q_{33}}, \quad \mathbf{j}_1 = \frac{1}{Q_{13} + \mathbf{k}Q_{33}}, \quad \mathbf{j}_2 = \frac{1}{Q_{13} - \mathbf{k}Q_{33}}, \\ \mathbf{j}_3 &= \frac{Q_{12} - 2Q_{32}}{4Q_{33} - Q_{11}}, \quad \mathbf{j}_4 = \frac{Q_{12} - Q_{23}}{Q_{33} - Q_{11}} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{j}_{b_1} = \frac{\mathbf{b}_r - \mathbf{b}_q}{Q_{33} - Q_{11}} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Substitution of Eq. (7) into Eqs. (5) and (6) yields

$$\mathbf{e}_r = -3\mathbf{r}\mathbf{w}^2 \mathbf{j}_0 r^2 + \mathbf{k} C_1 \mathbf{j}_1 r^{k-1} - \mathbf{k} C_2 \mathbf{j}_2 r^{-k-1} + 2\mathbf{j}_3 \mathbf{e}_1 r + \mathbf{j}_4 \mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{j}_{b_1} DT \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{s}_r = -\mathbf{r}\mathbf{w}^2 \mathbf{j}_5 r^2 + C_1 r^{k-1} + C_2 r^{-k-1} + \mathbf{j}_6 \mathbf{e}_1 r + \mathbf{j}_7 \mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{j}_{b_2} DT \quad (10)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{j}_5 &= (Q_{31} + 3Q_{33})\mathbf{j}_0, \quad \mathbf{j}_6 = \mathbf{j}_3(Q_{31} + 2Q_{33}) + Q_{32}, \\ \mathbf{j}_7 &= \mathbf{j}_4(Q_{31} + Q_{33}) + Q_{32} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{j}_{b_2} = (Q_{31} + Q_{33})\mathbf{j}_{b_1} - \mathbf{b}_r \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In order to derive the stiffness matrix, the radial displacements at the inner and outer surfaces are written in a displacement vector using Eq. (7),

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_w + \mathbf{u}_0 + \mathbf{u}_1 + \mathbf{u}_{DT} + \mathbf{G} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{C} \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= \begin{pmatrix} u_{r_i} \\ u_{r_o} \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{u}_w = -r\mathbf{w}^2 \mathbf{j}_0 \begin{pmatrix} r_i^3 \\ r_o^3 \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{u}_0 = \mathbf{j}_4 \begin{pmatrix} r_i \\ r_o \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{u}_1 = \mathbf{j}_3 \begin{pmatrix} r_i^2 \\ r_o^2 \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{u}_{DT} = \mathbf{j}_{b_1} \begin{pmatrix} r_i \\ r_o \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{DT}, \\ \mathbf{G} &= \begin{bmatrix} r_i^k & r_r^{-k} \\ r_o^k & r_o^{-k} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{j}_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{j}_2 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \mathbf{C} = \begin{pmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

In Eq. (13), r_i denotes the inner radius of a ring, and r_o the outer radius of a ring. The normal radial stresses at those two radii can be also written in a force vector using Eq. (10),

$$\mathbf{f}_b = \mathbf{f}_s + \mathbf{f}_0 + \mathbf{f}_1 + \mathbf{f}_{DT} + \mathbf{I}^* \mathbf{G} \mathbf{C} \quad (14)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}_b &= \begin{pmatrix} -r_i \mathbf{s}_{r_i} \\ r_o \mathbf{s}_{r_o} \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{f}_s = -r\mathbf{w}^2 \mathbf{j}_5 \begin{pmatrix} -r_i^3 \\ r_o^3 \end{pmatrix}, \mathbf{f}_0 = \mathbf{j}_7 \begin{pmatrix} -r_i \\ r_o \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{e}_0, \\ \mathbf{f}_1 &= \mathbf{j}_6 \begin{pmatrix} -r_i^2 \\ r_o^2 \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{f}_{DT} = \mathbf{j}_{b_2} \begin{pmatrix} -r_i \\ r_o \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{DT} \text{ and } \mathbf{I}^* = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Eliminating the constants \mathbf{C} in Eqs. (12) and (14) derives the relation of stresses and displacements at the inner and outer surface of each ring. The derived equation can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{k} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f}_b + \mathbf{f}_w - \mathbf{f}_{e_0} - \mathbf{f}_{e_1} - \mathbf{f}_{e_{DT}} \quad (16)$$

where

$$\mathbf{f}_w = -\mathbf{f}_s + \mathbf{k} \mathbf{u}_w, \mathbf{f}_{e_0} = -\mathbf{f}_0 + \mathbf{k} \mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{f}_{e_1} = -\mathbf{f}_1 + \mathbf{k} \mathbf{u}_1 \text{ and } \mathbf{f}_{e_{DT}} = -\mathbf{f}_{DT} + \mathbf{k} \mathbf{u}_{DT} \quad (17)$$

The ring stiffness matrix \mathbf{k} is

$$\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{I}^* \mathbf{G} \mathbf{F}^{-1} \mathbf{G}^{-1} = \frac{1}{z_2} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{k} z_1 Q_{33} - z_2 Q_{13} & -2\mathbf{k} Q_{33} \\ -2\mathbf{k} Q_{33} & \mathbf{k} z_1 Q_{33} + z_2 Q_{13} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where

$$\mathbf{z}_1 = \mathbf{z}^{-k} + \mathbf{z}^k, \mathbf{z}_2 = \mathbf{z}^{-k} - \mathbf{z}^k \text{ and } \mathbf{z} = \frac{r_i}{r_o} \quad (19)$$

The constant of axial strain \mathbf{e}_0 and \mathbf{e}_1 in Eq. (15) can be computed from force balance in the axial direction. Since there is no external axial force applied on the top and bottom surfaces, the summation of the axial forces over all the rings should be zero:

$$\sum_{j=1}^N 2\mathbf{p} \int_{r_i^{(j)}}^{r_o^{(j)}} \mathbf{s}_z^{(j)} r dr = 0 \text{ and } \sum_{j=1}^N 2\mathbf{p} \int_{r_i^{(j)}}^{r_o^{(j)}} \mathbf{s}_z^{(j)} r^2 dr = 0 \quad (20)$$

Eqs. (3)-(20) apply to any arbitrary ring. At each interface between two adjacent rings (e.g., j and $j+1$), the continuous radial traction and continuous radial displacement should be satisfied as follow follows;

$$\mathbf{s}_{r_i}^{(j+1)} = \mathbf{s}_{r_o}^{(j)} \text{ and } u_{r_i}^{(j+1)} = u_{r_o}^{(j)} \quad (21)$$

Combining all the ring stiffness matrix in Eq. (16) by using the continuity equations yields the global stiffness matrix equation. Finally, we can solve the system of $N+3$ equations and obtain the radial displacements $\mathbf{u}^{(j)}$ at each interface and constant axial strain \mathbf{e}_0 and \mathbf{e}_1 . The strains in cylindrical coordinates are then calculated using the relationship in Eq. (6).

A strength ratio at the element integration point is evaluated by using the stresses \mathbf{s} . 3-dimensional Tsai-Wu quadratic failure criterion is used [11].

$$\mathbf{s}^T \tilde{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{s} + \bar{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{s} R - R^2 = 0 \quad (22)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{F}}$ are strength parameters defined by the material strengths [11]. Solving Eq. (22) yields the strength ratio R

$$R = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{s} + \sqrt{(\bar{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{s})^2 + 4(\mathbf{s}^T \tilde{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{s})}}{2} \quad (23)$$

The calculated value of the strength ratio R greater than 1 indicates material failure, and thus has to be less than 1 for a safe design.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the stress and strength analysis in the previous section, a computer program ‘‘FlyComHHH’’ has been developed to calculate the stress and strength distribution in a hybrid composite rotor. The assumptions of a modified generalized plane strain (MGPS) as well as plane stress (PSS) are implemented in the program. All the two-dimensional analyses obviously neglect the edge effects at the top and bottom surfaces of the rotor. Thus, before employing the developed program for studying the hybrid flywheel, a three-dimensional finite element method (3-D FEM) is used to verify the accuracy of the two-dimensional analyses.

In 3-D FEM, the radial, circumferential and axial directions, 30, 12 and 10 elements are used, respectively. Each element is a 3-D layered brick element that can handle the varying material properties and thermally induced residual stress within the element. A composite material of Glass/Epoxy, T300/2500 and T800H/2500 with the ply angle $\mathbf{f} = 0^\circ$ are used and its material properties are listed in Table 1. The ply angle $\mathbf{f} = 0^\circ$ means a hoop winding angle. The inner and outer radii of the rotor are 50 and 100 mm, respectively, and the total height h of the rotor is given such that the height ratio with respect to the outer radius $h/r_o = 1$. The value for the curing temperature change DT and rotating speed \mathbf{w} are given -100°C and 60,000 RPM respectively.

The stress distribution using 3-D FEM is now compared with 2-D. The distributions of the stresses \mathbf{s}_q , \mathbf{s}_z , \mathbf{s}_r and strength ratio R for T300/2500 cases are obtained along the radial direction and given in Fig. 3.

The results using the MGPS analysis are in good agreement with those by FEM. Hence, it can be concluded that an assumption of MGPS can be safely employed in designing the composite flywheel rotor.

An optimal design of a hybrid composite rotor, by maximizing TSE without any material failure as formulated in Equation (1), is performed using a combination of composite materials with different fiber types: (A) Glass/Epoxy, (B) T300/2500, (C) T800H/2500. Their material properties are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Material Properties of Glass/Epoxy, T300/2500 and T800H/2500 considered for the optimization.

Material Property	A	B	C	Unit
	Glass/Epoxy	T300/2500	T800H/2500	
E_{qq}	38.6	130	155	GPa
$E_{zz}=E_{rr}$	8.27	9	9	GPa
$G_{qz}=G_{qr}$	4.14	4.55	4.55	GPa
G_{rz}	4.14	4.55	4.55	GPa
$n_{qr}=n_{qz}=n_{rz}$	0.26	0.3	0.3	
X	1062	1800	2900	MPa
X'	610	1400	1600	MPa
Y	31	80	70	MPa
Y'	118	168	168	MPa
S	72	48	48	MPa
α_x	8.6	-0.3	-0.3	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
α_y	22.1	28.1	28.1	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
r	1800	1600	1600	kg/m^3

Fig. 3 Distribution of stresses and strength ratio along the radius calculated by 2D analyses(MGPS, PSS) and 3D FEM analysis for composite flywheel rotor.

Optimizations are performed combining up to three different composite rims and can thus be grouped into 3 categories. In the first category, only one material is used, and in the second category, two materials, and so on. In each category several cases of material selections and sequences are considered and listed in Table 2. Each thickness of composite rim is considered as design variables.

The initial thickness for each composite rim is 20 mm, and the inner radius of rotor is 50mm. The values for the curing temperature change DT and rotating speed w are -100°C and 60,000 RPM, respectively. To avoid inaccuracy in the optimization process, the minimum value for the ring thickness is set to 0.01 mm, below which the material is no longer considered.

The calculated optimal design variables and TSE are listed in Table 2. In the first part, the thermally induced stresses are not considered. Whereas, in the second part the thermally induced stresses are introduced by $DT=-100^\circ\text{C}$. It is noted that in cases of 2-2 and 3-3 each thickness of material A and B is converged to zero values, respectively. This happens due to an improper selection of material sequence: the sequence is not in the order of increasing circumferential Young's modulus E_q . For example, in case 3-4 of B-C-A material sequence, the thickness of material A is converged to zero. All the cases of the thickness converging to zero are indicated by a superscript (*) on the material in Table 2.

As noted in the stress distribution, the effects of the curing temperature on the optimal design are significant. For instance, the results of the optimal designs using the material sequence A-B-C show that TSE with consideration of DT reduces by about 30 %.

The distributions of the circumferential, axial and radial stress and strength ratio for (part I, part II) optimization CASE3-1 is shown in Fig. 4.

Table 2 Optimization results for the selected material sequences; The superscript (*) in the material sequence indicate a material which thickness is converged to a zero value.

PART I : $w=60,000\text{ RPM}$ and $DT=0^\circ\text{C}$							PART II : $w=60,000\text{ RPM}$ and $DT=-100^\circ\text{C}$						
CASE	Material Sequence	$r_1(\text{mm})$	$t_1(\text{mm})$	$t_2(\text{mm})$	$t_3(\text{mm})$	TSE(Wh)	CASE	Material Sequence	$r_1(\text{mm})$	$t_1(\text{mm})$	$t_2(\text{mm})$	$t_3(\text{mm})$	TSE(Wh)
CASE 1-1	A	50.00	38.60	-	-	64	CASE 1-1	A	50.00	37.61	-	-	61
CASE 1-2	B	50.00	93.77	-	-	435	CASE 1-2	B	50.00	80.35	-	-	292
CASE 1-3	C	50.00	94.04	-	-	438	CASE 1-3	C	50.00	76.97	-	-	262
CASE 2-1	A - B	50.00	33.76	75.26	-	660	CASE 2-1	A - B	50.00	28.19	68.79	-	480
CASE 2-2	B - A*	50.00	93.80	0.00	-	435	CASE 2-2	B - A*	50.00	80.78	0.00	-	296
CASE 2-3	B - C	50.00	59.15	45.60	-	586	CASE 2-3	B - C	50.00	49.32	38.87	-	371
CASE 2-4	C - B*	50.00	94.05	0.00	-	439	CASE 2-4	C* - B	50.00	0.00	80.28	-	291
CASE 2-5	A - C	50.00	38.53	75.89	-	756	CASE 2-5	A - C	50.00	32.78	67.46	-	525
CASE 2-6	C - A*	50.00	94.05	0.00	-	439	CASE 2-6	C - A*	50.00	77.94	0.00	-	270
CASE 3-1	A - B - C	50.00	33.80	41.78	44.22	858	CASE 3-1	A - B - C	50.00	28.26	38.14	38.82	597
CASE 3-2	A - C - B*	50.00	38.50	76.38	0.00	764	CASE 3-2	A - C - B*	50.00	32.79	67.49	0.00	526
CASE 3-3	B* - A - C	50.00	0.00	38.53	76.17	761	CASE 3-3	B* - A - C	50.00	0.00	32.86	67.37	525
CASE 3-4	B - C - A*	50.00	59.04	45.54	0.00	584	CASE 3-4	B - C - A*	50.00	49.21	38.92	0.00	370
CASE 3-5	C* - A - B	50.00	0.00	33.83	75.24	661	CASE 3-5	C* - A - B	50.00	0.00	28.25	68.74	480
CASE 3-6	C - B* - A*	50.00	94.03	0.00	0.00	438	CASE 3-6	C* - B - A*	50.00	0.00	80.75	0.00	296

A:Glass / Epoxy
B:T300/2500
C:T800H/2500

Fig. 4 Distribution of stresses and strength ratio for (Glass/Epoxy+T300/2500+T800H/2500).

All the calculated optimum TSE are shown in Fig. 5 where each bar indicates location of each rim and thus the length of the bar means the thickness of each rim. It can be obviously noted that the number and sequence of materials are very important in maximizing TSE or minimizing the stresses inside the materials. The stress distributions are effected by the sequence of stiffness, mostly circumferential Young’s modulus E_q . Softer materials inside of the rotor which are easier to expand in the radial direction and stiffer materials outside of the rotor which experience less radial displacement eventually reduce the radial stresses.

PART I : $w=60,000$ RPM and $DT=0^\circ C$

PART II : $w=60,000$ RPM and $DT=-100^\circ C$

Fig. 5 Comparison of optimal thickness of composite rims and the corresponding TSE for various selections of composite material. (Part I: $w=60,000$ RPM and $DT=0^\circ C$; Part II: $w=60,000$ RPM and $DT=-100^\circ C$)

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